

**Real-Time, Real Impact: How Synchronous Sessions Advance Student Learning in
Foundational Online Courses**

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Abstract

While asynchronous design remains the backbone of online education, this paper examines how the strategic addition of synchronous Live Learning sessions can enhance student outcomes without creating undue burden for instructors. Drawing on findings from a quasi-experimental study of two foundational online courses, the analysis demonstrates that synchronous sessions produced measurable gains in areas requiring complex skill development and real-time feedback, while showing little effect on outcomes tied to content recall. Building on these insights, the paper advances three themes, online course design, faculty development, and institutional leverage, that translate empirical results into actionable strategies. By reframing synchronous instruction as a purposeful, targeted intervention, the discussion emphasizes how institutions and instructors can design for maximum impact with minimum overload, ultimately strengthening student engagement, progression, and overall learning outcomes.

Keywords: synchronous instruction, online learning, faculty development, learning outcomes, cognitive load, live sessions.

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Online learning has long been celebrated for its flexibility; however, this flexibility also introduces distance between the instructor and student, between the student and content, and sometimes between the student and success. As institutions work to close those gaps, synchronous learning opportunities have emerged as a kind of connective tissue: real-time, human-centered moments that can reframe a course from something students do alone to something they do with support. The rapid growth of fully online programs, particularly those serving adult learners, has heightened the urgency of this challenge. While asynchronous models provide accessibility and scalability, they can unintentionally foster isolation, limiting opportunities for immediacy, feedback, and interaction. Institutions are increasingly seeking strategies that balance flexibility with enhanced student engagement and persistence.

The researchers in a previous study examined this promise in action (Shehadeh & Pritts, 2025). Specifically, we discussed the use of structured, required synchronous Live Learning sessions embedded in two foundational online courses: English Composition (ENG 121) and Introduction to Film (ENG 225). The findings revealed more than a modest increase in engagement or pass rates; they demonstrated measurable differences in student performance on specific learning outcomes, differences that could not be attributed solely to attendance.

Building on these findings, this paper examines how institutions and faculty developers can apply these insights to develop practical teaching strategies. Specifically, it examines how structured synchronous interventions can be integrated into online course design, how faculty development initiatives can support effective implementation, and how institutions can leverage these practices to enhance student engagement and strengthen overall learning outcomes.

Framework or Theoretical Perspective

At first glance, synchronous sessions in asynchronous courses may seem like a contradiction, an interruption to flexibility, and a potential burden to both students and instructors. However, beneath that surface tension is a deeper opportunity: real-time instruction can create the kinds of interpersonal and cognitive support that asynchronous design sometimes lacks. The previous study and the development approach proposed in this paper are guided by two frameworks that help explain why (Shehadeh & Pritts, 2025).

The first is instructional immediacy, the idea that student learning is influenced not only by content but also by how present and responsive the instructor appears to be. In online classrooms, where physical presence is often absent, immediacy must be constructed through tone, presence, pace, and interaction. Synchronous sessions offer a built-in opportunity for that construction. They allow instructors to answer questions as they arise, clarify confusion in the moment, and respond to student cues, verbal or otherwise, that rarely surface in discussion boards or written feedback alone.

The second guiding framework is cognitive load theory, which reminds us that more is not always better. In fact, poor instructional design, especially in live formats, can overwhelm learners. The key is to structure synchronous sessions intentionally: focusing them around high-leverage content, breaking information into manageable segments, and creating space for practice or application. When conducted effectively, these sessions reduce confusion, increase confidence, and foster readiness for more complex tasks (Sweller, 2011).

Blau et al. (2017) demonstrated that real-time engagement influences perceived learning and academic performance, with significant effects stemming from how content is delivered and the naturalness of the communication. Taken together, this helps shift the conversation away

from whether synchronous sessions are “good” or “bad” and toward a more nuanced question: how can we design real-time instruction that feels helpful, not heavy, for both students and instructors? Together, these frameworks illuminate the findings of the previous study and provide a foundation for translating them into concrete practices in course design, faculty development, and institutional strategy, as discussed below.

Approach or Case Context

This case draws on findings from a quasi-experimental study conducted at a fully online institution that primarily serves adult learners balancing education, employment, and family responsibilities (Shehadeh & Pritts, 2025). The study examined the instructional impact of required synchronous Live Learning sessions embedded within two foundational courses: English Composition (ENG121) and Introduction to Film (ENG225). These courses were selected because they are entry-level requirements, representing critical points of persistence for new students in online programs.

The rationale for focusing on this context stems from the broader challenges of online learning, where adult learners frequently encounter barriers to engagement, connection, and sustained academic progress. Embedding synchronous sessions within the existing asynchronous course structure provided a practical way to test whether intentional real-time interaction could enhance student performance and retention.

This approach contributes to understanding the topic by highlighting whether students attended these sessions and how their performance on course learning outcomes (CLOs) shifted as a result. By comparing two matched student groups across both courses, those enrolled in sections with required synchronous sessions and those without, the study offers evidence-based insights into the effectiveness of targeted synchronous interventions in online learning. These

findings serve as a foundation for exploring how institutions, faculty developers, and course designers can integrate such strategies to improve learning outcomes at scale.

These results clarify how value is activated. In the sections that follow, the applied recommendations are drawn directly from the conditions under which outcomes improved: sessions were aligned to specific learning outcomes, pre-structured for purposeful interaction, and integrated into the course flow rather than added on. The aim is not “more live,” but better live, targeted, sustainable, and designed to help students practice complex skills with timely support. Table 1 summarizes observed differences in CLOs between sections with required Live Learning and sections without, by course and outcome focus.

Table 1. Summary of CLO impact by condition (Live Learning vs. No Live)

Course	CLO Focus (short)	Observed Effect of Live Learning	Instructional Implication
ENG121 (English Composition)	Argument construction	Improvement observed	Use live time to model reasoning and claim–evidence linkage
ENG121 (English Composition)	Evidence integration	Improvement observed	Practice sourcing and citation decisions in real time
ENG121 (English Composition)	Concept/terminology recall	Little to no difference	Keep recall in asynchronous materials
ENG225 (Introduction to Film)	Formal analysis	Improvement observed	Walk through analysis steps with exemplars and feedback
ENG225 (Introduction to Film)	Applying critical frameworks	Improvement observed	Use guided application to new clips/examples
ENG225 (Introduction to Film)	Element identification/recall	Little to no difference	Reserve for readings, short videos, or auto-graded practice

Note. “Improvement observed” indicates CLOs where sections with Live Learning outperformed sections without; “Little to no difference” indicates outcomes where live time did not yield a measurable advantage. Table 1 reflects findings synthesized in this paper; no new analyses are introduced.

Analysis or Discussion

Building on the findings of the previous study, we propose three themes to guide the integration of synchronous Live Learning into online education: online course design, faculty development, and institutional leverage.

1. Online Course Design

Research consistently shows that student engagement and persistence in online education are tied to opportunities for interaction and connection (Martin & Bolliger, 2018; Tinto, 2017). The integration of synchronous sessions into otherwise asynchronous courses suggests that intentional design can strengthen student outcomes by reducing feelings of isolation and clarifying expectations. Online courses can be structured to include targeted live sessions at key points in the term, such as early in the course to build community, mid-course to deepen engagement with complex concepts, and near the end to support application and synthesis. Embedding these sessions into the course architecture, rather than treating them as optional add-ons, ensures alignment with CLOs and provides a consistent framework for engagement.

2. Faculty Development Initiatives

Faculty capacity to design and deliver practical synchronous sessions is central to their success. Studies highlight that many instructors default to replicating lecture-style delivery in synchronous spaces, which limits interaction (Fabriz et al., 2021). Professional development should therefore emphasize strategies for designing interactive, outcome-driven sessions that complement asynchronous learning rather than duplicate it. Tools such as breakout rooms, polls, and collaborative documents can foster active participation, while training on equitable teaching

practices ensures that all students feel included and valued. Development initiatives may consist of workshops, peer observation cycles, or communities of practice that showcase effective models. Such programs not only build teaching competence but also reinforce faculty confidence in engaging students synchronously.

3. Institutional Leverage

At the institutional level, integrating synchronous learning offers strategic opportunities to enhance engagement, progression, and retention. Strong faculty-student connections, fostered by real-time interaction, are associated with higher persistence rates in online programs (Kahu & Nelson, 2018). Institutions can leverage these findings by embedding synchronous elements into foundational courses, monitoring performance outcomes, and scaling practices that demonstrate the most substantial impact. Beyond metrics, positioning synchronous interventions as part of a broader *culture of care* signals an institutional commitment to student success. This approach not only enhances learning outcomes but also strengthens student satisfaction and the institution's reputation.

Together, these themes illustrate how synchronous learning can be more than a temporary intervention; it can serve as a strategic design principle for online learning environments. By drawing on the literature and linking course design, faculty development, and institutional policy, these findings contribute to a growing body of evidence that supports blended approaches in online higher education.

Conclusions and Implications

Shehadeh and Pritts (2025) confirmed that synchronous Live Learning sessions can positively impact student performance in online courses, particularly on CLOs tied to higher-order skills such as drafting, revising, and applying formal analysis. The evidence suggests that

synchronous time is most effective when used intentionally to provide real-time modeling, scaffolding, and feedback, rather than for content delivery or unstructured Q&A. These findings align with prior research, which shows that synchronous learning environments are most impactful when structured, purposeful, and designed to enhance engagement (McBrien et al., 2009).

The implications are clear: Live Learning should not be viewed as a wholesale replacement for asynchronous design, but as a targeted tool that amplifies learning when aligned with complex skills. For faculty, this means approaching synchronous sessions as opportunities to help students practice and apply their learning in ways that are not easily achieved independently. For institutions, it highlights the value of strategically integrating synchronous moments into course design and supporting faculty with training and resources that focus on designing purposeful, high-impact sessions.

At a broader level, these findings suggest that Live Learning can enhance both student engagement and faculty satisfaction when implemented with care and intentionality. Rather than adding to instructor workload, well-designed synchronous moments can serve as meaningful interventions that benefit both learners and educators. Future research should explore scalability across disciplines, long-term effects on persistence and completion, and the balance between synchronous and asynchronous modalities that best support adult learners in fully online contexts. Ultimately, the promise of Live Learning is not more time on screen, but a more sustainable approach to teaching and learning. When real-time sessions are targeted, structured, and aligned to high-leverage outcomes, they strengthen learning while respecting the bandwidth of students and instructors. This is the core of sustainable education in online contexts: practices that are impactful, repeatable, humane, and built to last across courses, terms, and teams.

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